

Policy Brief

to the Executive Council

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Title: Policy options to Reduce Greenhouse Gas Emissions

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Deputy Minister: Ministry of

- Environment
- Economic Development (Industries, Trade and Commerce)
- Energy and Natural Resources
- Agriculture
- Transport

Summary

The proposal aims at providing policy options aimed at reducing green house gas emissions to address concerns on climate change and impact on environment in the province. The policy brief explores various options for reducing carbon emission and intends to arrive at a right and balanced portfolio of market-based and non-market environmental policy instruments to meet the expected outcomes. The initiative is led by the ministry of environment in consensus with various stakeholders and other related ministries.

Objectives

- Reduce greenhouse gas emissions and maintain thresholds of rising temperatures within 2°C in line with OECD recommendations

Outcomes Sought

- Minimize impact on environment with due focus on growth and sustainability
- Promote innovation and sustainability while reforming carbon markets

Financial Impact

- Yes, this is a one of the key components of multi-year transformation program (3 – 5 years)

Considerations impacting timing of decisions

- A tactical immediate approach for addressing operational challenges
- The tactical approach aligning with a long-term transformation program to meet strategic goals

Recommendation

- A)
- B)

Policy Options to Reduce Greenhouse Gas Emissions: A ‘systems thinking’ approach

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Abstract

The proposal aims at providing policy options aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions to address concerns on climate change and its impact on the environment in the province. The policy brief explores various options for reducing carbon emission and intends to arrive at a right and balanced portfolio of market-based and non-market environmental policy instruments to meet the expected outcomes. The initiative is led by the ministry of environment in consensus with various stakeholders and other related ministries.

Background

Threats posed by global warming and climate change are real and has far-reaching implication on the life on earth over the long run. Global warming is the rise in temperature of the earth’s climate system and is a long-term phenomenon with drastic consequences. Greenhouse gas (GHG), including carbon dioxide (CO²) emissions, contribute directly towards an increase in the temperature of the earth’s climate system. The concentration of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere in parts per million has risen over 40% since the industrial revolution in the mid-eighteenth century and reflects the contribution of human activities towards climate change. The Rio Earth Summit in 1992, which led to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change has pledged to reduce the emission of greenhouse gases and thereby cut down the carbon footprint leading to global warming. This was followed by the Kyoto Protocol, which sought various governments to reduce greenhouse gas

emissions, based on scientific consensus, and the Paris Agreement. The Paris Agreement aims at limiting global warming to less than two degrees Celsius and pursue efforts to limit the rise to 1.5 degrees Celsius. The agreement also targets to reach zero net emissions by the end of the century. Jurisdictions across the world have been making attempts to meet the goals outlined by the Paris Agreement through effective policy interventions. This paper outlines the scope and evaluates policy options for the province to meet the objectives for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and thereby reduce carbon footprint and meet environmental protection and sustainable development outcomes.

Key Issue

Jurisdictions across the world, and specifically among the OECD nations are proactively combating the challenges presented by climate change and global warming. The key of concern is to regulate and reduce the emission of greenhouse gases linked to any form of human activity. Scientists across the world unanimously agree that global greenhouse gas emissions must be cut by as much as seventy percent below the 2010 levels by 2050. This interim target is well aligned with that of the Paris Agreement which seeks to reach zero net emissions by the end of the century, and thereby limit the increase in global mean temperature to 2°C above preindustrial levels. To achieve these targets, the province needs to adopt a long-term environmental strategy and make policy interventions that will serve as a pathway to environment

protection and limit impacts due to human activities and the emission of greenhouse gases.

Approach

The need to proactively address greenhouse gas emissions requires the province to have a strategic approach for identifying the sources of greenhouse gases and have a comprehensive set of policy options to respond. It is also important to have an evidence-based approach, with the right level of focus and intervention, that can maximize the effectiveness of interventions. Techniques to assess the effects of policy interventions before implementation, and the ability to measure their effectiveness after implementation are important to assess the success of various policy interventions. This helps in benchmarking policy interventions when it comes to comparing the intended outcome and actual outcome.

Figure 1. Policy Approach for Reducing Greenhouse Gas Emission

The approach is iterative and needs to be continuous and adaptive till the desired outcomes are achieved. There are plenty of elements in the jurisdiction responsible for the emission and absorption of greenhouse gases. The

emission elements are sources and absorption elements are sinks. The sources that contribute to emission can range from those involved in energy generation, such as coal, transport, agricultural and industrial waste etc.

Figure 2. Breakdown of Canada's emissions, total 704 Mt CO₂ eq (Source: Environment Canada)

While sinks such as forests not only reduce emissions but also helps to remove CO₂ from the atmosphere.

Stakeholder Analysis and Consultation

There are diverse stakeholders who need to be consulted and engaged during the policy process for reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The policy for greenhouse gas emissions will have implications on businesses, industries, agriculture, forestry, financial and research institutions, NGOs etc. Though the responsibility for the implementation is within the purview of the ministry of environment, there is substantial overlap with the functions of other ministries such as that of economic development (industries, trade and commerce), energy and natural resources, agriculture and transport.

Figure 3. Environment Outcomes & Stakeholders (Simplified)

It is crucial to ensure that the environmental outcomes achieved by reducing greenhouse gas emissions are progressive, realistic and well-aligned with other facets such as that of optimal economic development, sustainability and innovation.

Jurisdictional Research and Review

The greenhouse gas emissions among the OECD countries, both by volume and by per capita was studied in detail to understand where Canada is positioned among peer nations. A study of policy interventions adopted by other jurisdictions is also reviewed to determine the context and relevance of policy interventions adopted to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

(a) by per capita

b) by volume

c) by change

Figure 4. OECD Greenhouse Gas Emission Statistics
 Source - [Environment at a Glance 2015, OECD](#)^[7]

The report “Environment at a Glance -2015”, published by OECD compares various nations and it can be observed that the Scandinavian and the Western European Nations have made massive progress in reducing greenhouse gas emissions. For instance, the European Union has a target of cutting greenhouse gas emissions by 20% by 2020 compared and has to be complied by the member states. It has also implemented an emissions trading system. Some of the Scandinavian countries have been on a path to a society free of fossil fuels while achieving economic progress. On the other hand, countries such as Sweden have been innovative in their environmentally friendly technological advancements, while, Norway has leveraged a relatively high carbon tax as a policy tool to reduce the carbon footprint. To summarize, countries often use a mix of market and non-market-based policy interventions that are successful in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and the carbon footprint, while ensuring growth, economic progress and sustainability.

Assessment of Alternatives

There are various approaches from a policy standpoint to meet environmental outcomes and achieve the targets for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and the resultant carbon footprint.

The goals for reducing the carbon footprint can be achieved broadly in four ways:

- a) Reducing direct greenhouse gas emissions
- b) Switching to renewable sources
- c) Increasing efficiencies
- d) Introducing sinks for greenhouse gases

These options inter-operate with one another and influence the net greenhouse gas emission and the net carbon footprint. The objective would be to lower the overall net output which has an impact on the environment.

From a policy standpoint, interventions can again be broadly classified into two as:

- a) Market-based policy interventions
- b) Regulatory / non-market policy interventions

Market-based instruments seek to influence desirable behaviour by adjusting cost structures linked with emissions to promote incentives for reduced emission and cost-effectiveness. However, it is important to ensure that these instruments do not result in market irregularities.

Carbon taxing or carbon pricing is a market-based intervention that increases the cost of fuels contributing to greenhouse gas emissions and carbon footprint. Increase prices can lead to lower demands and revenues generated from taxes can be leveraged to fund compensating initiatives.

Emissions trading is another form of market-based policy intervention which aims to influence behaviours resulting

in reduced greenhouse gas emissions. Instead of fixing a price in the form of a tax, the trading system sets caps on emissions and issues emission allowances. The allowances are traded in the market and are often allocated or auctioned.

Removal of subsidies for environmentally harmful activities and those leading to emissions is another form of intervention that attains outcomes similar to market-driven interventions.

Non-market-based intervention such as regulatory and compliance requirements for reporting emissions by business, promoting green technology adoption, removal of entry barriers to such solutions, supporting innovation etc. also serves to accomplish environmental outcomes and reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

In addition to the above options, market segments responsible for positively reducing the carbon footprint also needs to be factored in to devise policy instruments that incentivize these segments. For instance, the biofuel industry, green technology industry, public transit systems etc.

Risk Assessment and Evaluation

The different policy options mention in this paper comes with risks that are wide-ranging and hence important to mitigate during implementations. The market-based policy intervention such as emission trading brings along risks related to measurements. It should be possible to accurately measure the initial emissions and to determine how it changes over time, to determine the success of an emission trading system. The setting of caps requires realistic measurement capabilities without which the system can be jeopardized. On the other hand, carbon taxes have the risks of increasing prices which can potentially affect the lower-income groups in the society. It is therefore important to perform a detailed risk analysis

and evaluation before choosing the policy option for reducing greenhouse gas emission.

Solution Proposal

The best approach for reducing carbon emission would be by leveraging the right portfolio of market-based and non-market environmental policy instruments.

The first step to arriving at this mix is to determine all the sources responsible for carbon emissions, their weightage and the markets contributing to it. For example, carbon emissions caused by fossil fuel burning in the utility industry, refining industry etc. and the use of automobiles for personal and commercial purposes etc. The market segments responsible for positively reducing the carbon footprint also needs to be incentivized, i.e., the biofuel industry, green technology industry, public transit systems etc. While the trading permits are sometimes negatively perceived as licenses for polluting, they can be extremely useful in industries such as the utility industry. This when combined with a non-market policy instrument imposing costs associated with non-compliance works well to reduce the overall carbon emission footprint

In other areas such as the use of automobiles and related carbon emissions, carbon tax, which is often calculated as a percentage of the volume and price of fuel consumed, is an efficient policy instrument to reduce the overall carbon dioxide footprint.

Non-market-based environment policy instruments such as regulations for industries to measure and report carbon dioxide emissions, fines for non-compliance etc. are also important to achieve the policy goal.

It is very important to take a systemic view to arrive at the right portfolio of policy instruments that aims to optimally reduce carbon dioxide emissions, e.g. to optimally reduce carbon dioxide emissions from the generation of electricity from fossil fuels and the use of electric cars.

Figure 5. Policy options/portfolio for Greenhouse Gas Emissions (See Appendix)

The annexure illustrates the scenario for subsidies for home insulation as the policy means to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and its analysis from a systemic perspective.

References

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Appendix

Appendix 1 - Policy options / portfolio for Greenhouse Gas Emissions

Appendix 2 – Systems Analysis of Impact of Home Insulation Subsidies